

AGU24 Abstract Draft

Title: US River Hydrokinetic Technical Resource Characterization and Assessment

The U.S. Department of Energy conducted a comprehensive assessment of the riverine hydrokinetic energy resource in the continental U.S. (CONUS) in 2012, estimating a theoretical resource of 1,300 TWh/yr and a technical resource of 99 TWh/yr. However, the best available hydrologic model data at the time was the National Hydrography Dataset Plus V1 (NHDPlusV1) of mean annual discharge and bulk velocity. A National Academy of Science review determined the methodology using this data and the recovery factor approach, an indirect calculation based on factors approximated under different flowrate-slope scenarios at a selected site, were not sufficiently robust to provide an estimate of the technical resource in rivers and streams, which exhibit large annual and interannual variation of flow. For the present study, we reassess the technical resource using an improved hydrologic model dataset and methodologies, including the sensitivity of the technical resource estimates to technology constraints like device efficiency and device density. Our technical resource assessment uses hourly stream bulk velocities from the recent National Water Model (NWM) Retrospective v2.1 dataset published in 2021, which covers a 42-year period between February 1979 and December 2020 encompassing over 2.7 million river segments. We estimate the overall national technically recoverable resource and its geographic distribution by examining flow statistics, estimated channel shape, and an assumed device diameter and density at each segment. The improved data and methodologies enable a technical resource assessment that address the distribution of the resource across the range of flows by direct calculation at all segments. This revised riverine hydrokinetic resource assessment will be disseminated through the USDOE's marine energy atlas to facilitate regional energy planning, project siting and development of river hydrokinetic projects throughout the CONUS.

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